

PEDAGOGICAL CONTENT OF THE FORMATION OF COGNITIVE COMPETENCE OF FUTURE TEACHERS OF MUSIC EDUCATION

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Abstract. The article talks about the importance of improving the professional and pedagogical skills of students of music education and professional knowledge, which is one of its branches. Today, the activities emphasize the effectiveness of the music teacher, preparation for the start of teaching activity, and, first of all, the importance of pedagogical skill, mastery of the types of competencies necessary in each pedagogical process. The cognitive competence of music education students in the process of conducting music education lies in the fact that students regularly update their professional knowledge, gradually develop skills and subsequently teach as music teachers and solve problems independently. thinking, it is proposed to improve his cognitive psychology using effective methods of the pedagogical approach.

Key words: Personality, society, thinking, cognitive competence, interdisciplinary thinking, cognitive personality, cognitive development, concept of music.

INTRODUCTION

Today, it is undoubtedly true that the main goal of the education system is to teach learners (students, pupils) to think. Higher-level cognitive skills such as logical thinking and critical thinking are key skills for everyday life, in addition to academic achievement in school and higher education. To improve educational standards, the nature of cognitive development must be understood in all components of education, such as curriculum development, teaching practice, and assessment. But unfortunately, cognitive development is often used to discuss whether curriculum topics are appropriate for students' levels. In their professional, practical activity, teachers do not engage in teaching that helps students develop high-level cognitive abilities. Sometimes teachers ignore whether their teaching practices contribute to the cognitive development of pupils and students..

MATERIALS AND METHODS.

From scientists of the Commonwealth of Independent States, great importance is attached to the development of musical education through scientific researches aimed at professional competence and cognition: B.S. Gershunsky, V.P. Bezpalko, I.V. Snigirov, B. G. Asafev, B. L. Yavorsky, A. B. Goldenweiser, D. B. Kabalevsky, O. A. Apraksina, E. B. Abdulin, Y. B. Aliev, L. G. Archajnikova, A. N. Leybovich, G. A. Ball, S. E. Shishov.

Focusing on the development of general knowledge and various skills of students of early childhood music education, while considering important issues in the formation of cognitive competence. Let's look at some aspects of some cognitive Keeling.

Studying Music Concepts and Basic Principles: Students will increase their understanding of music by studying the fundamentals of music, instrumental and vocal notations, musical genres, and conceptual works.

Analytical thinking and discussion skills: In the formation of cognitive competence, attention is paid to students learning to analyze and discuss musical works and their performance. They are taught to play music, analyze and interpret their thoughts.

History of Music and History of Uzbek Music: They understand the history of music by studying the history, themes, key figures and key performers of Uzbek music.

Creativity and creativity: In the acquisition of cognitive competence, students are focused on the development of creativity and creativity within music. In their own environment, they learn to perform concepts and create new pieces of music.

Experience and Practice: Students will learn important discussions and introductions to practice music priorities, performance and other skills they have learned, collaborate with the community, and promote their own development.

Through this information, students in early childhood music education use different ways and methods to build their cognitive competence. Experiential and theoretical lessons, practical training, analysis and other educational processes are very important for the development of these competencies.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Pedagogical skill is very important in the content of the pedagogical process aimed at forming the cognitive competence of the future teacher of music culture, which includes musical pedagogical creativity, the ability to solve educational situations and problems, pedagogical technology and cognitive competence in innovative education covers the formation of qualities such as understanding.

When organizing a pedagogical process aimed at forming students' cognitive competence, it is necessary to pay special attention to the following:

- 1) encourage students to ask many questions and support this habit;
- 2) encouraging students' independence and increasing their responsibility;
- 3) creating an opportunity for students to organize independent activities;
- 4) focus on students' interests.

The following factors hinder cognitive development in a person:

- 1) avoiding risks;
- 2) allow rudeness in thinking and behavior;
- 3) underestimation of personal fantasy and imagination;
- 4) subordination to others;
- 5) thinking only about success in any case.

One of the most important issues is the formation of the professional cognition of future music teachers through specialized classes, as well as the education of the psychophysiology of students in the study of specialized subjects. In particular, paying special attention to the fact that one of the important factors affecting the methods and means of developing the cognitive abilities of elementary school students is teacher-student cooperation is one of the topical issues of specialization and specialty sciences. It is known that the educational process has a two-way character and consists of equal relations between the teacher and the students. It is necessary to properly organize the educational process of the teacher who leads this process, and it includes an important pedagogical process.

The goal of the modern pedagogical education system is to achieve general and professional development of a new category of music teacher. Because the educational institution places high demands on the music director regarding his professional

qualifications and personal qualities. Any pedagogic profession is a complex and exciting process, therefore, this profession makes many demands on the future music teacher, no matter what field it belongs to. The goal of all areas of education is to educate a well-rounded person. But in this regard, the main role is played by the aesthetic disciplines - music, fine and applied arts, literature and their interrelationships in educational institutions. In particular, music classes in educational institutions, music teachers should also have special knowledge, skills and qualifications, pedagogical skills and pedagogical skills. It is known that music lessons include four musical processes:

The teacher actively participates in the lesson. Providing education and training to students, carrying out educational and methodical work, participating in organizational work, active participation in social life are the main aspects of a teacher's activity. Providing knowledge to students occupies an important place in the activity of a pedagogue. Delivering the knowledge system that meets the requirements of the time to the student, making them interested in learning, and achieving the student's activity in acquiring knowledge is required in the pedagogical process of today's specialty and specialty sciences.

The process of musical education is very complicated. There is no limit to musical knowledge. The process of pedagogical cooperation between a student and a teacher in specialized subjects has its own characteristics and includes the following:

- forcing the future music teachers not to be indifferent during the lesson, to master the specialty through creative activities, to create and search, to think independently;
- ensuring that students have a constant interest in knowledge during the educational process of specialized subjects;
- strengthening the student's interest in knowledge in specialized subjects with an independent creative approach;
- organization of the teacher's and student's activities in cooperation.

It is up to the teacher and the student in the pedagogical process aimed at the formation of students' creative competence in specialty and specialty classes, which technology they choose to achieve the goal, because the main goal of both sides is clear: to achieve the result, which is used depending on the level of knowledge of the students, the nature of the group, and the circumstances. the technology is chosen, for example, for the achievement of the result, maybe a film, distribution material, drawings and posters, various literature, information technology will be needed, which depends on the organization of the pedagogical process.

Together with the teacher, it is necessary to plan the teaching process in advance, in this process, the teacher must take into account the unique aspect of the educational subject, the place and conditions, the ability and need of the student, as well as his ability to organize cooperative activity, only then, the necessary rewarded result can be achieved. In short, the student should be brought to the center of education.

The teacher should be able to see each specialty lesson as a whole and design the future lesson process in order to imagine it. It is very important for the teacher to draw up a technological map of the upcoming lesson, because the technological map of the lesson is created based on the characteristics of the subject, the subject taught for each subject, the capabilities and needs of the students. It is not easy to make such a technological map, because it is necessary for the teacher to be aware of pedagogy, psychology, special methods

and information technologies, as well as specialized disciplines. Making each lesson colorful and interesting depends on the carefully designed technological map of the lesson.

How to create a technological map of the lesson depends on the teacher's experience, goals and discretion. No matter how the technological card is structured, it should reflect the lesson process as a whole, and the clearly defined goal, task and rewarded result, the technology of organizing the lesson process should be fully expressed. The structure of the technology card saves the teacher from writing an extended outline of the lesson, because all aspects of the lesson process are reflected in such a card.

A technology card like the one made by the teacher for each subject of the subject, each lesson, helps him to imagine and understand the subject as a whole (one semester, one academic year) according to), helps to start the whole learning process, from the goal to the result to be achieved. In particular, the construction of the technological card based on the student's capabilities and needs will make it possible to bring him as a person to the center of education and increase the effectiveness of education.

In the process of teaching, students are treated as individuals, various pedagogical technologies and modern methods are used to improve their executive skills, independent, free thinking, research, creative approach to every issue, sense of responsibility, conducting scientific research, analysis, to make effective use of specialized sciences and scientific literature; most importantly, it strengthens interests in study, science, pedagogy and the chosen profession.

Achieving such a result in professional activity requires the use of innovative and information technologies in the educational process. We will dwell on some of them. We will give a detailed understanding in the "Technology and design of music education" training manual. The modern methods presented in this study guide, or technological trainings that help increase the effectiveness of teaching, develop specialization, executive skills, logical, mental, creative, critical, cognitive, communicative independent thinking in students, develop their abilities, become competitive, mature specialists. helps them to become and develop the professional qualities needed by the specialist. This process is influenced by the student's life experience, existing knowledge, the presented system of knowledge, and his attitude to studying science. Students do not have the same opportunities in this field. Students who have extensive knowledge, rich life experience, and mastered study skills are successful in their studies. The acquisition of knowledge is influenced by the student's previously acquired educational skills and competencies. According to psychologists, mastering knowledge means incorporating newly received information into the student's previously available information system. The wider the student's knowledge, the easier it is for him to accept new information.

It is also necessary to pay attention to the fact that the teacher must restore the information of the student about the newly studied topic, create a basis for mastering the topic. Especially when starting a new topic, asking students interesting questions and creating problematic situations increases interest. The teacher should use methods of work that bring maximum benefit to the student.

From a psychological point of view, the student's cognitive process includes perception, perception, memory, thinking and imagination. Sensation and perception are the first, simplest stage of knowledge. In perception, the characteristics of the impressions of the external world are reflected separately in the brain. In perception, a complete image of this impression is formed in the brain.

Perception is a complex reflection stage compared to intuition, which is influenced by a person's age, education, life experience, speech, attitude to the object of perception, mental state, etc. The inner world of a person is formed on the basis of intuition and perception.

Memory ensures that these perceived and perceived impressions are stored in the brain. Memory is the settling, storage, and later restoration of the impressions of the external world in the human mind. Great attention should be paid to each stage of memory in the educational process. It is useful to focus on the memorization stage. Because a well-remembered impression remains in the memory for a long time. For example: important dates in the life of every person are always clearly remembered - birthdays, the first day of going to school, the birth of a child, receiving an award, etc. Because such solemn (some sad days) have a strong impact on a person's personality and remain firmly in the memory.

This feature of memory should be used in the educational process. It is necessary to explain the vital and scientific importance of the material delivered to the student, create problem situations, and pay attention to using the material in effective ways.

For a long time, knowledge was imparted based on memory in the educational process. Such teaching is called traditional teaching.

Today's educational processes consist of unique educational processes. Interactive educational processes are of great importance in acquiring knowledge. We will consider some of them below.

Innovation and novelty are two aspects of the development of society in culture, education and in general. Based on the various relationships between traditions and innovations, cultural scientists distinguish society into traditional and modern. In a traditional society, tradition dominates over innovation. In modern societies, innovation is considered a basic value.

The teacher's cognitive development develops in the course of lessons in direct connection with the introduction of innovations. The main goal of innovative education is to create a sense of responsibility for the future and self-confidence in students. The group of scientists led by J. Botkin described innovative education as the main type of knowledge acquisition as an alternative to traditional, i.e. "normative" education in the "Club of Rome" lecture. Normative education is "directed at mastering the rules of behavior in repetitive situations", while innovative education envisages the development of the ability to act together in new situations.

The case-study interactive teaching method is one of the most preferred methods by the students. The reason for this can be seen in the fact that this method gives the listeners the opportunity to take the initiative, gain independence in mastering the theoretical situation and forming practical skills. On the other hand, it is of particular importance that the analysis (analysis) of the situations can have a strong influence on the process of professional formation of the listeners, serve their "growth" from a professional point of view, interest in learning and positive motivation.

In music education, it is necessary to deeply teach the theoretical foundations of art and through this to explain the social significance of art and the processes related to it, to show the effectiveness of the artistic-aesthetic effect, and to determine its social significance on a scientific basis. . These include, first of all, the objects and events of the existing reality, which are related to the object and subject of perception; secondly, it directly concerns the group of artistic and creative people, as well as institutions and associations that promote and spread

artistic values. The third component consists of a set of values that have taken place in the system of social-aesthetic relations, and the fourth is made up of art lovers formed under the influence of art, literature, art and literary criticism. It is necessary to understand the desires of these layers, the worldview of accepting art, the characteristics of the works they are demanding, in general, to understand the demands and needs of the social environment through them and to have the skills to explain it to their students.

Modeling is the optimal way to properly and purposefully organize the research process. As part of the process, the goal of developing a pragmatic, systemic-functional model was defined. This type of model allows future teachers to search for means of developing their knowledge of the basics of improving the information culture development system in the pedagogical process. As a model subject, the level of preparation of students helps to reflect the control functions of the researched processes that allow to achieve the difference between the initial and final state.

The model of improvement of the system of development of informational culture of future teachers represents goal orientation, theoretical-methodological, meaningful-processual, organizational-pedagogical and result-oriented components (see Figure 2).

In our model, the concept of "cognitive competence" is used to describe a complex integrated object or the state of dependence of individual components of the educational process, as well as to create a whole from various components.

Analysis class - in the process of music literacy, listening to music, and singing, attention is paid to perfect analysis of the works. Detailed analysis of the works, i.e. providing information about their authors, determining the tempo, rhythm, measure, tone, tonality, dynamics, form of the work, what team or orchestra it was written for, determining the genre, its ideological essence. , the study of the artistic image creates a basis for mastering musical-theoretical knowledge through the work. It depends on the creativity of the teacher how to organize the analysis lesson and in what direction. Such lessons are primarily intended for practical purposes. Analytical lessons teach students to think freely, make them think, face various problems and encourage them to solve them.

Conversation lessons are one of the important means of making the process of acquiring musical-theoretical knowledge lively and interesting. Organizing and conducting lessons in the form of conversation requires creative research from the teacher. The determining factor of the teacher's skill is to conduct the conversation based on a clearly structured plan and in a way that is directed towards a certain goal. In the course of the conversation lesson, the student learns to think independently and express his opinion. Effective, interesting, information-rich conversation depends on the teacher's leadership skills, the ability to formulate questions and choose them correctly. Conversation lessons are one of the most effective ways to check acquired musical-theoretical knowledge. The effectiveness of conversation lessons depends on the clear and good understanding of the topic by the interlocutors, and the fact that the questions asked during the conversation are clear and succinct. Questions are asked orally and answered in the same way. The teacher observes the mistakes in the students' answers and corrects them if necessary. In the conversation, you can talk about a song you learned independently, a piece of music you listened to, a concert you watched or a musical show. The teacher must have announced the topic of the lesson in advance. The teacher asks the prepared questions and the students start

answering. Other students fill in the incomplete answers. The teacher leads the conversation and ensures active participation of students.

The duties of the teacher in conversation classes are as follows:

1. Preparing interesting and vital questions for the interview.
2. Emphasize that the questions fully cover the topic.
3. Creating conditions for students to freely express their thoughts.
4. To make the questions systematic and consistent.
5. Involve all students in the conversation.
6. To be able to look at each other with respect during the conversation.
7. Be an example to students in dealing.
8. Summarizing ideas and drawing conclusions.

Musical field trips are organized by traveling to the composer's house museums, concerts, music festivals, music competitions, or by making a musical field trip with the help of a video tape, in order to learn the sources of musicology, to study the work of a particular composer. One of the important conditions is that the objects of travel are directly related to the subject of the lesson. This, in turn, is much more effective than classroom lessons, and will remain in the minds of students for a long time.

Formation of knowledge and skills of young people. Teachers-pedagogues should introduce modern programs to education in the formation of knowledge and skills of students in general secondary schools, in order to achieve their perfection, to achieve professional development, drawing conclusions from the above points. To the extent that the student is involved in acquiring more knowledge and developing creative abilities, the effectiveness of the lesson and the correct implementation of youth education will be achieved. For this, it is necessary to thoroughly master extracurricular activities, activities of clubs, and achieve voluntary organization of students' free time.

A systematic approach to the development, implementation, and evaluation of instrumental performance teaching and learning, research on human learning and interpersonal communication in a goal-oriented manner. based on the result and dealing with animate and inanimate means of more effective organization of the educational process.

Enjoying the classic and modern values of our people in the lessons of music culture is necessary for the effectiveness of the lessons, as well as in visual arts. During the lesson, the teacher is not limited to listening to music and singing or drawing, but can conduct interesting open dialogues on the topic of "Manners - human adornment" and use the teachings left by our great ancestors.

For example, in elementary school music lessons, students can be taught to think independently by learning songs to the tune of music and discussing love for our country, mutual respect, and etiquette. based on the content of the song, children can be asked to draw pictures, so that the images of the flag and the bird in our coat of arms come alive.

Naturally, music directs the inner and outer world of a person to beauty and goodness through melodies. That is, the emotions that people need to have are also in music, for example, the national song is combined with beautiful movement, politeness and cheerfulness. It should be noted here that a polite child will be kind to his modest, gentle, and humble parents. I don't like rude, conceited, arrogant children. In the same way, an unpleasant song or unpleasant pictures make a person angry.

By learning educational songs during the lesson, students' creative perception increases, they think independently, and the ability to compare images develops. A student who can think independently learns the song taught by the teacher correctly, sings paying attention to its content and sings it effectively.

Based on the topic, the music teacher should ask the student such a question that the very simple and interesting question turns into a debate. In 45 minutes, the teacher-educator should show himself to the students through greeting etiquette, speech culture, artistic-imagery, high pedagogical skills, creativity. When organizing a lesson, the teacher must take into account the age and interest of the student, so that his students can think independently and learn from their teacher.

In the development of professional education, teachers and pedagogues should use their creative abilities to make students-young people mature and educate them to be educated and educated. Nothing can be an obstacle for this. Today, the organization of modern classes based on new pedagogical technologies is the demand of the time for education and upbringing of students.

"First of all, young people who study the Internet and strive for new things should be able to think independently, to strengthen the perception of music, and also to have the ability to speak civilly. Only a polite and civilized person can search and learn something on the Internet. In particular, it is necessary to learn the norms of morality, to strive for perfection in the child, to expand the scope of knowledge, to study the way of life.

Based on the program, textbooks, methodical manuals, recommendation letters, work plans on specific topics are being created, because, due to the nature of music, it is able to strongly influence human emotions, as well as bring students into the world of sophistication, form music perception, and increase musical literacy. and is an important means of moral-ideological education.

The student quickly learns the songs of this method. They feel the sweetness of the tunes, but the folk songs and statuses given in the seventh grade are difficult for students studying in general secondary schools to learn. It is appropriate to give such songs to vocational educational institutions.

CONCLUSION

In short, cognitively thinking people are becoming more important than ever in the conditions where information technology has advanced and as a result of the creation of artificial intelligence, jobs performed with various mechanical movements can be performed by robots. Based on the above opinions, we found it permissible to define the concept of a creative person as follows: "Cognitive person" is a creative person who can combine previously existing ideas in a new form.

In order to educate cognitively thinking persons, it is necessary to properly train children in the family. We can make the following suggestions and recommendations in this regard.

It is necessary for us to establish proper upbringing of our children in the family, not after reaching adulthood, but from childhood. We should create conditions for them to express their opinion independently and respect these opinions.

We should teach our children not only to memorize knowledge in certain fields of science, but also to increase their assimilation of necessary professional knowledge, to be able to deeply analyze the essence of the issue.

The role of the environment in the education of a cognitive personality is of great importance, and we should create a healthy scientific environment for our children along with their education. Having an environment in which they can freely express cognitive thinking along with creative ideas, whether in the family, at school or with friends, is the first step in putting cognitive ideas into practice.

Of course, parents should be patient in raising cognitive individuals. When our children make a mistake, instead of hitting them hard without understanding the essence of the problem, we should explain the reasons for their mistakes and teach them ways to eliminate them. After all, according to the laws of philosophy, cause creates effect.

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